

Predicting Material Properties of Recycled Carbon Composite Using a Detailed Simulation Approach

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Abstract:

The recycling of thermoplastic carbon fiber-reinforced composite through shredding offers a cost-effective and energy-efficient alternative to methods like pyrolysis or chemical decomposition, particularly when the fiber-matrix bond is retained in the process [1, 2]. The resulting chopped fiber bundles can be reprocessed into semi-aligned organosheets. However, the heterogeneous nature of the bundle distribution leads to significant variability in mechanical performance, necessitating predictive simulation tools. This paper presents a novel representative volume element framework tailored for recycled, chopped, thermoplastic carbon fiber-reinforced composites. By shifting from fiber-scale to meso-scale modeling, the simulation captures bundle interactions and accounts for variations in length, orientation, and cross-sectional geometry. Three bundle shapes—cylindrical, elliptical, and rectangular—are assessed with respect to their influence on fiber volume content and resulting stiffness. The simulation is implemented in Abaqus using the Micromechanics Plugin. The findings show that rectangular bundles yield the highest Young's modulus and fiber volume content, though all shapes underperform compared to orthotropic laminates of the virgin material. Limitations in current random placement algorithms are discussed, along with ongoing developments in packing strategies, contact modeling, and RVE size convergence. This work contributes toward a multiscale simulation approach for optimizing recycling processes and predicting the mechanical behavior of chopped fiber composites.

1 Introduction

The recycling of thermoplastic carbon fiber-reinforced composites (CFRPs) is often complex and energy-intensive, as thermoset plastics need to be separated from the fibers via pyrolysis or chemical process. This often results in an additional degrading through the loss of interface on the fibers [1, 2]. The matrix can stay on the fiber when using a thermoplastic. Through a cost-effective shredding process the thermoplastic CFRP can be recycled and the chopped fiber bundles can be pressed into a thermoplastic organosheet (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Raw material of thermoplastic chopped carbon composite and a carbon composite plate (organosheet) produced from it.
Source: Marzieh Alikouchaki @ TU Clausthal

With a variation in bundle length, size and distribution the material properties can vary greatly. Therefore, a quick simulation process is needed. The use of representative volume elements (RVE) offers a fast prediction of global or homogenized material properties of complex material mixtures and are therefore also used in carbon composites. Continuous carbon fibers can be predicted with simplified 2D-models through the use of periodicity and symmetry [3]. For short fibers at least a 3D-model is necessary, as they are randomly distributed, which also leads to a lower fiber volume content (FVC) [4, 5]. Yet homogenized material properties can be still calculated and often get applied for injection molded parts. With complex multi-scale simulations prediction of flow-induced fiber orientation and localized material properties in a part are possible [6]. Therefore, RVE should with some changes predict also the material properties of recycled, randomly chopped carbon composite.

Recycled, chopped, thermoplastic CFRPs result in long, discontinuous bundles embedded in the matrix. These bundles are neither continuous nor randomly dispersed individual fibers, making classical 2D RVE approaches insufficient. Some studies have explored voxel-based macro-scale models, but the bundles are limited to the element- and voxel-sizes [7]. Thus a novel RVE framework is needed for simulating meso-scale features of recycled shredded CFRP (Figure 2).

This paper explores what the new requirements are, how such a framework could look like and what shape should be used as an approximation.

Figure 2: Process of predicting the material properties of recycled material using a detailed simulation of prevalent effects. Adapted from [8].x

2 Requirements for Novel RVEs

Instead of modeling single fibers, the new RVE must simulate interactions between entire bundles, shifting the focus from micro- to meso-scale. These bundles are significantly larger than individual fibers and dominate the mechanical response. Fiber bundles are highly variable in size and shape. Unlike the standard cylindrical geometry used in continuous fiber RVEs, recycled bundles may be rectangular, elliptical or irregularly cut. A proper bundle shape model is essential for accuracy.

Furthermore, the length, positioning and orientation have a high variation between the bundles. Depending on the shredding and following sifting method different distribution types than just uniform or normal distribution are possible and need to be represented in the model. Often a main orientation can be observed.

The bundles are often ten times longer than the plate thickness, resulting in a semi-oriented material with pronounced in-plane characteristics. To still represent all effects and to have a full bundle in the RVE, the sides have to be uneven and thus eliminating the validity of periodic boundary conditions.

3 Model Setup

The modeling approach aims to replicate the actual microstructure observed in recycled thermoplastic CFRP plates, where fiber bundles are stochastically distributed and vary in size, orientation, and interaction (Figure 3a). To explore the most suitable geometric representation of fiber bundles in recycled composite materials, three different bundle shapes were evaluated: cylindrical, elliptical, and rectangular (Figure 3b).

Figure 3: (a) Example of recycled fiber bundles on a measuring plate. (b) Approximated basic shapes for the RVE set up.

The RVE is defined with a dimension of 50 mm x 50 mm x 3 mm, to ensure enough fiber bundles are fully placed in the model. This is significantly bigger than conventional RVEs. While the positioning and in-plane orientation are uniformly distributed over the RVE size, the size of the bundles is normally distributed with a mean length of 18 mm and a standard deviation of 3 mm or 2 mm. The other dimensions also follow a normal distribution (see Table 1). The number of placed bundles varies with the shape, as cylinder geometrically have lower packing density than the other shapes.

Table 1: Geometric mean value with their standard variation and quantity of different fibre bundle types used in the simulation. d1 = Length [mm], d2 = Width/Diameter 1 [mm] & d3 = Height/Diameter [mm].

Type	d1	d2	d3	Num. of Bundles
Cylinder	18.0 ± 3.0	1.1 ± 0.2	/	82
Elliptic Cyl.	18.0 ± 2.0	1.5 ± 0.24	0.5 ± 0.05	121
Rectangle	18.0 ± 2.0	2.2 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.05	108

The generation of the RVE begins with setting the input parameters as given above (Figure 4, right side). Each bundle is created with a randomized position and inplane orientation within the RVE domain. The out-of-plane tilt is introduced through a normal distribution. This accounts for realistic angular variations observed in physical samples.

Figure 4: Process flow of creating a fitted RVE for random chopped CFRP.

To ensure physical plausibility, a collision detection algorithm is created in python with the cadquery library. It checks whether the new bundle overlaps with any previously placed ones. Only non-intersecting bundles are accepted and added to the simulation. This iterative procedure continues until the desired number of bundles is reached or a maximum number of attempts is exhausted (see result in Figure 5).

Figure 5: Random distribution of different bundle shapes in a RVE. Top right: cylindrical, top left: elliptical, bottom: rectangular

Once the fiber bundle configuration is finalized, the remaining matrix domain is generated by subtracting the fiber volume from the RVE, effectively intersecting the assembly with the outer RVE box. Any fiber bundle extending beyond the boundaries of the RVE is trimmed accordingly.

The complete geometry, comprising fiber bundles and matrix, is then transferred to Abaqus for mechanical simulation. Material properties are assigned

to both phases: the bundles are modeled as unidirectional carbon composite laminates using data for Toray Cetex TC1225 [9], while the matrix is treated as a homogeneous thermoplastic using experimentally determined properties of LM-PAEK from Victrex with a Young's modulus of 3630 MPa and a tensile strength of 80 MPa.

The meshing is carried out using tetrahedral elements due to the complex intersections between bundles and matrix. A base mesh size of 0.8 mm is used, with refinement down to 0.4 mm in regions with higher geometric complexity. Taylor or Uniform Surface Gradient boundary conditions are applied, as periodic conditions are not valid for this non-symmetric and irregular geometry. The analysis and post-processing are performed using the Micromechanics Plugin in Abaqus, allowing the homogenised engineering constants (E_1 , E_2 , E_3) to be extracted from each RVE (Figure 4, left side).

4 Analysis of RVEs

The RVEs show a Young's modulus in E_{11} direction from 5300 to 6400 MPa for cylindrical to rectangular shape, respectively (Figure 6). With a random, yet uniform orientation of the bundles, the modulus in the cross section E_{22} is nearly identical to the E_{11} direction for elliptical and rectangular shapes, only the cylindrical bundles show a slight difference from 8%.

All Models show a significantly higher modulus than the matrix with only around 3600 MPa. Yet the E_{11} modulus for an orthotropic laminate is with around 69000 MPa ten times higher than observed in the RVEs.

Figure 6: Homogenized modulus in E_{11} direction & Young's Modulus of the matrix.

The highest volume of bundles (16.4%) is created with the rectangular shapes. The elliptical shapes show 15.8% and the cylindrical shapes show only 13%.

With a fiber volume in the bundles of 66% the FVC is 10.8%, 10.4% and 8.6% for the rectangular, elliptical and cylindrical shape, respectively.

Surprisingly, the RVE with elliptical shapes has the highest number of bundles (121), but not the highest FVC. All dimensions are also selected to have a similar cross-section. Variation in volume can occur through the combination of random values in the normal distribution and the rejection of individual bundles during collision testing.

Figure 7: Measured bundle fraction of the RVE and calculated FVC for each geometry.

5 Discussion

New requirements for RVEs simulating random chopped CFRP were presented. The biggest change is from individual fiber to fiber bundles, which changes the scale from micro to meso. Additionally, the size of the bundles is long compared to the plate thickness, thus leading to unsymmetrical sides of the RVE. This can be solved using Taylor boundary conditions. Furthermore, the fiber length and size follows a distribution, that is a critical input for the simulation. The random placement algorithm generally performs well, achieving realistic fiber orientations. However, early bundles tend to dominate orientation due to packing constraints. The calculated moduli are all an improvement to the pure matrix and nearly double as high. Yet the difference to an orthotropic laminate is ten times higher. While there needs to be a lot of improvement, the correlation between stiffness and FVC is good. Which means an improvement in package density will also bring the

material properties closer to the laminate.

The estimated FVC of the produced plate is around 50%, which is much higher than the 15-30% of conventional short fiber composites. However, all models underperform in FVC. At least one finding could be made regarding the shapes: a greater number of bundles does not necessarily lead to a higher FVC. For example, the elliptical shape has 121 bundles, yet the rectangular shape has the highest FVC.

The method enables the simulation of various realistic distributions, as well in bundle size as in direction. Nevertheless, the placement strategy requires further development to improve packing density and contact control.

6 Ongoing Work

While the current modelling approach demonstrates promising results in reproducing the spatial and directional characteristics of fiber bundles, several limitations have been identified, particularly with respect to bundle orientation and packing density. One observed challenge is that the first bundles tend to dominate the orientation field, with subsequent bundles conforming to available gaps, leading to a biased distribution.

To address this, more advanced placement algorithms are under investigation. One such approach involves gap-filling techniques that iteratively insert smaller bundles into voids left between previously placed bundles. Another promising strategy is to prioritize the placement of longer bundles first, which could help establish a more representative distribution and maximize fiber volume content.

In addition, dropping algorithms are being developed to ensure there is always direct contact between the bundles. This changes the out of plane angle dependent on the already placed bundles.

The costliest method would be to run a preliminary simulation to mimic the real-world deposition of bundles during the press processing, thus allowing the bundles to settle under process-induced pressure, potentially resulting in more realistic interactions such as contact, nesting, or slight undulation.

As further produced plates will have additional matrix material for easier postprocessing and shaping, an effect of matrix infusion into the bundles should be considered. But first a change in real test specimen needs to be observed.

To improve computational efficiency and ensure statistical representativeness, studies are also planned to determine the minimum RVE dimensions necessary to achieve homogenized material properties with minimal variation between different realizations. This will support the development of a robust, multiscale simulation workflow capable of guiding optimization in recycling process parameters.

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